

Preparative, Structural and Thermal Studies on some Chelate Polymers

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Chelate polymers of bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn have been prepared from bis-mercaptoacetamide ethylenediamine (BMAED). The analytical data agree with 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry. Elemental analysis, magnetic, spectral and thermal properties of polychelates have been studied and probable structures are assigned to the chelate polymers. All the chelates are amorphous powders, insoluble in common organic solvents. The sequence of thermal stability predicted on the basis of decomposition temperatures and activation energy was found to be Ni > Mn > Cu > Co > Zn. Whereas kinetic and thermodynamic parameters were calculated from dynamic TGA by the use of Sharp-Wentworth and Freeman-Carroll methods.

Recently considerable interest has been created to obtain polymers in which the molecular skeleton is formed by coordinate links through metal ions or atoms. The first row transition metals are characterised by their ability to form a wide range of coordination complexes in which the octahedral, tetrahedral, and square-planer stereochemistry predominate. This inspired us to prepared monomeric ligand which would be able to form complexes with a variety of transition metals.

The present communication describes the preparation and characterisation of chelates prepared from BMAED derived from thioglycolic acid with ethylenediamine. The probable structures of these chelates have been determined on the basis of their elemental analysis, magnetic moment and electronic and infrared spectral data. Thermal (TG) properties were studied with a view to compare the thermal stability. The thermal stabilities found by decomposition temperatures is in agreement with activation energies.

Results and Discussion

All the polychelates are coloured and amorphous in nature. They are insoluble in common organic solvents. The elemental analyses data (Table 1) agree with a 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

Ir spectra: Comparison of ir spectra of the chelates and ligand reveal that the spectra of polymeric chelates do not significantly differ from each other but they do differ from that of the ligand in some characteristic frequencies. Sharp bands observed at 3 320 (NH) and 1 340 cm^{-1} (C—N) in the spectra of ligand are shifted to a lower frequency region by 10—15 cm^{-1} in the polychelates suggesting coordination of metal ions through nitrogen of the NH group¹. The weak band observed at 2 600 cm^{-1} (SH) in the free ligand² disappears in chelates showing that the M—S bond is formed due to deprotonation of the SH group³. A band at 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=O) in the ligand is found unaltered in all the chelates suggesting the absence

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA OF POLYCHELATES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Metal	μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_{max} cm^{-1}	Assignment
	C	H	N	S				
BMAED	34.10 (34.00)	5.62 (6.76)	13.24 (13.46)	29.20 (30.00)	—	—	—	
$\{[\text{Mn}(\text{BMAED})]\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$	27.02 (27.38)	3.50 (3.80)	10.94 (10.64)	24.90 (24.34)	21.70 (20.89)	5.12	22 120 ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4A_1(G) {}^4E(G)$ 20 000 ${}^6A_1 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(G)$ 25 380 CT	
$[\text{Co}(\text{BMAED})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]_n$	23.65 (23.92)	4.62 (4.65)	9.83 (9.30)	22.80 (21.00)	22.93 (21.58)	4.91	9 009 ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ 18 018 ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ 24 474 CT	
$[\text{Ni}(\text{BMAED})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}]_n$	23.80 (23.94)	4.59 (4.65)	9.02 (9.31)	22.02 (21.60)	21.28 (20.50)	3.81	9 515 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3E_g(F)$ 15 410 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ 24 390 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$	
$\{[\text{Cu}(\text{BMAED})]\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$	26.54 (26.94)	3.40 (3.71)	9.83 (10.38)	22.70 (22.74)	24.10 (23.50)	1.67	15 620 ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ 24 096 CT	
$[\text{Zn}(\text{BMAED})]_n$	26.45 (26.50)	3.55 (3.68)	9.99 (10.31)	24.58 (23.50)	24.48 (24.90)	Dia.	—	

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of coordination through oxygen of C=O⁴. In the spectra of the polychelates new bands observed in the region 300—560 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to M—S and M—N bonding⁵. The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polychelates exhibit weak bands at 765 and 1 580 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to coordinated water. This is further confirmed by TG analysis⁶.

Magnetic moment and electronic spectra: The magnetic moment and reflectance spectral data of the polychelates are shown in Table 1. The magnetic moment of the Cu^{II} polychelate is 1.67 B.M. which is lower than expected and this may be due to weak exchange coupling. The reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} polychelate exhibits two bands in the expected region for square-planar copper(II)⁷. The Ni^{II} polychelate shows magnetic moment of 3.21 B.M. which is close to the range (2.8—3.3 B.M.) observed for octahedral stereochemistry⁸. The reflectance spectrum of the Ni^{II} polychelate shows three bands in the expected region for octahedral geometry⁹. This structure is further confirmed by the ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.68) which is close to the value expected for octahedral structure¹⁰. The Co^{II} polychelate has a magnetic moment (4.91 B.M.) expected for three unpaired electrons, which offers the possibility of octahedral symmetry¹¹. Its reflectance spectrum shows three bands in the region expected for octahedral geometry¹². The magnetic moment (5.12 B.M.) for the Mn^{II} polychelate is lower than spin-only value (5.92 B.M.) for five unpaired electrons in a tetrahedral environment¹³. The reflectance spectrum of the Mn^{II} chelate shows intense bands in the normally expected regions for tetrahedral structure¹⁴. The Zn^{II} polychelate is found to be diamagnetic as expected. From ir, electronic spectra, magnetic measurements and elemental analysis, the following structure may be suggested for all the metal chelates.

M=Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}; for Mn, Cu and Zn chelates the coordinated H₂O molecules should be absent.

Thermal study: The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polychelates lost water near 150—220°, corresponding to two coordinated water molecules per repeating unit. The Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} polychelates lost water at 144°, which are probably crystal water¹⁵. The observed weight-loss is a little higher than that required in this region and this may be due to some other chain degradation reactions involved in pyrolysis of the chelate polymer¹⁶. The TG curves of polychelates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with BMAED depict that final decomposition products correspond to Mn₂O₄, Co₃O₄, NiO, CuO and ZnO respectively¹⁷. The decomposition temperature of the polychelates decrease in the order: Ni > Mn > Cu > Co > Zn. The sequence of thermal stability of the polymers predicted on the basis of the initial decomposition temperatures is in harmony with that predicted from the thermal activation energy values¹⁸ (Table 2). Thermodynamic parameters¹⁹ for all the polychelates were found to be nearly the same, which indicates a common reaction mode²⁰. Low values of frequency factor (*Z*) conclude that the reaction of the decomposition of polychelates can be classed as 'slow' reactions²¹.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. DMF was used after distillation. Thioglycolic acid and ethylenediamine were purified by conventional methods.

Preparation of ligand: The ligand (BMAED) was prepared by the condensation of thioglycolic acid with ethylenediamine. A mixture of thioglycolic acid (0.2 mol) and ethylenediamine (0.1 mol) was heated on an oil-bath for 8—10 h in CO₂ atmosphere and the temperature was maintained at 115°. On cooling a brown solid was obtained. It was liquified with 1N HCl and the resulting solid was washed with boiling water, recrystallised from ethanol and dried at 60°, m.p. 178°.

Preparation of polychelates: An equimolar mixture of the ligand and metal acetate dissolved in minimum volume of DMF (40 ml), was digested for 1 h on a water-bath. The resulting solid was washed with DMF, absolute alcohol and hot distilled water and air-dried.

The magnetic susceptibility was determined as room temperature by the Gouy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer. The TG thermograms were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer instrument. Elemental analysis was carried out on a Coleman C-H-N analyser. The metal contents were estimated by oxide method and sulphur by Messenger's method.

TABLE 2—THERMOANALYTICAL DATA OF POLYCHELATES OF BMAED*

Compd.	Decomp. temp. (°C)	W %	Activation energy kJ mol ⁻¹		ΔS J	ΔF kJ	S^* J	Z s ⁻¹	n
			FC	SW					
{Mn-BMAED}H ₂ O _n	390	79.50	35.69	33.98	-317.72	135.18	-107.96	79.68	0.67
[Co-BMAED.2H ₂ O] _n	340	77.40	22.94	24.20	-322.02	123.72	-108.51	63.48	0.60
[Ni-BMAED.2H ₂ O] _n	420	76.20	40.12	34.40	-307.81	136.51	-96.72	113.66	0.57
{Cu-BMAED}H ₂ O _n	370	75.70	25.20	22.94	-316.25	124.18	-107.92	75.68	0.53
[Zn-BMAED] _n	320	77.50	17.76	17.72	-324.53	119.33	-107.38	89.07	0.72

*W % = Weight-loss due to oxidation-reduction ; f C = Freeman-Carroll ; SW = Sharp-Wentworth ; n = Order of reaction.

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